

RESEARCH AND PEDAGOGIC INTERVENTIONS

PEER - REVIEWED RESEARCH JOURNAL IN EDUCATION

GBCTE

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A STUDY ON STUDENT'S USAGE OF CELL PHONE IN CLASSROOM

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Abstract

This study assessed the opinions of students and teachers on classroom cell phone usage and the perceived impact of student use of cell phones during class on the teachers. Study found that on average, students were using their phones almost seven times per class and it had negative side effects with their academic achievement. Majority of teachers considered it distracting to their teaching.

Introduction

The increase in student's cell phone usage in classrooms has led to a decrease in academic performance and satisfaction with instruction (Dietz & Henrich, 2014). However, it is unknown as to whether the usage of cell phone by student classroom has any effect on the teacher. Using cell phones for non-task related purposes during class time has been shown to have negative outcomes on student learning; it also has a negative effect on the students in close proximity. When a teacher sees a student texting,

or using his or her phone inappropriately, it may have a negative impact on the teacher's ability to teach. The perceived impact of cell phone usage among students on teachers is yet to be explored. Thus, the present study examines the effect of non-educational cell phone usage by students on teachers.

Objectives

The Objective of this study was to determine student and teacher opinions of classroom cell phone usage and the perceived impact of student use of cell phones during class on the teachers

Hypotheses

I. Students will be more likely to believe that cell phones should be allowed in class than teachers.

II. Students will be more likely to believe that individuals have the ability to multitask compared to teachers

III. Teachers will be more likely to think cell phone usage of students during class time is a distraction compared to students.

Sample: Participants consisted of 163 students from five undergraduate colleges selected on convenience.

Sixty-one percent of the students who completed the survey were female. Faculty in the same colleges completed a slightly different survey ($N = 289$). 60% of the teachers and faculty who completed the survey were female. The mean years of teaching among those who completed the survey was 15.04 years, with overall years of experience ranging from 1 to 55, with a standard deviation of 10.73.

Instrumentation

A student self-report questionnaire containing 13 items and a teacher self-report questionnaire containing eight items was used to assess attitudes

about cell phone use in college classroom, as well as demographics. The questionnaires used were based on questions used in a previous study by Tindell (2012). For the items in the current study, participants were asked to respond to yes or no questions, open-ended questions, and interval scales questions; each item was scored as a standalone construct.

Procedure

For the student portion of the sample, questionnaires were administered through general education classes. Questionnaires were administered to the faculty portion of the sample through the college e-mail system. Data was collected during the 2014-2015 academic year.

Results

The following section describes: (a) general descriptive statistics on student and teacher cell phone usage, (b) student and teacher opinions on whether cell phones should be used during classroom and student rationale for their opinion, (c) student and teachers' beliefs about multitasking, and (d) teacher cell phone distraction beliefs and how teachers handle distraction. To analyze the results, teacher and student answers were

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TABLE 1 : bring cell phone to class					
Groups	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	Not Responded
Teachers	287	1.68	.82	.05	2
students	159	1.08	.27	.02	4

compared using chi-squared tests, t-tests, and frequency counts.

Cell Phone Usage of Students and Teachers :

To investigate if there is a difference between the number of student using a cell phone while teaching, students and teachers who bring their phones to class, an independent t-test was conducted. Table 1 is a t-test of how often students and teachers bring their phones to class with an alpha level of .05. Students and teachers selected one of three options (1 = Yes, always; 2 = Yes, sometimes; or 3 = No, never) to indicate how often they bring their phones to class. The mean response for teachers (M = 1.68, SD = .82) was significantly different from the students' responses (M = 1.08, SD = .27, $t(384.23) = -11.21$, $p < .05$, $r = .50$). This indicates that students are significantly more likely to bring their phones to class than teachers.

When asked, on average, how many times students use their phones during

class time, the mean teacher response was 6.68 times per class, with a range of 0 to 75 times and a standard deviation of 9.87. When asked, on average, how often the teachers have been distracted by a their responses were as follows: 14% never, 19% once per semester, 21% once a month, 29% weekly, 13% daily, 5% multiple times per day.

When students were asked how easy it is to send or receive text messages in class without the instructors being aware, they answered on a Likert scale from 1 to 7 (1 = very difficult, 4 = neither difficult nor easy, to 7 = very easy). The mean response was 4.61 with a standard deviation of 1.57.

A chi-square statistic was conducted to investigate whether students and teachers differ on typical cell phone status during classroom instruction. Pearson chi-square results indicate that teachers and students significantly differ on the typical status of their cell during class ($\chi^2(4, N = 428) = 130.7$, $r = .48$). These results show that teachers are more likely to

Groups	Phone off	on but away	On & occasionally check	On & regularly check	On & check notification
Teachers	73 (27%)	175 (65%)	19 (7%)	1 (<1%)	1 (<1%)
students	8 (6%)	61 (38%)	77 (48%)	7 (5%)	6 (3%)

Groups	NO	YES but use minimum	YES use as they please
Teachers	180(63%)	86(30%)	22 (7%)
students	59(37%)	82(50%)	22(13%)

have their cell phones put away and that students are most likely to check their phones periodically during class. Table 2 shows the frequencies and percentages for teachers versus students across response options.

Research Questions

Hypothesis number one investigated if students and teachers differ on whether cell phones should be used during classroom instruction, and a chi-square statistic was conducted to answer this question. Table 3 shows the frequencies and percentages for teachers versus students across response options.

Pearson chi-square results indicate that teachers and students significantly differ on whether or not students should be allowed to use cell phones during class ($\chi^2(2, N = 451) = 28.93, r = .25$). Students are more likely than teachers to think that cell phones

should be allowed during classroom instruction.

Tables 4 and 5 depict the rationales for why students chose whether or not they should be allowed to use cell phones during class. Two individuals read all of the responses for the different possible rationales and created coding groups for each possible response. After the categories were established, each individual rated the responses from the separate categories. Upon completion of initial coding, the two raters had an 88% inter-rater agreement for the "No" rationale, a 92% inter-rater agreement for the "Yes, but usage should be kept to a minimal"

Rationale	Frequency
Distraction	30 (57%)
Not Beneficial for Class	13 (25%)
Disrespectful	6 (11%)
Emergency	4 (7%)

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rationale, and an 89% inter-rater agreement for the "Yes, as much as they please." After discussion and debate over the coding responses, there was a 100% inter-rater agreement for all the rationales.

Hypothesis number two investigated

Table-5: Student's rationale for using phones in class

Rationale	Frequency
Personal Choice	29 (31%)
Emergency	23 (25%)
Beneficial to Class	22 (24%)
Important messages/ Other Responsibilities	9 (10%)
Not an Issue/ Distraction	6 (6%)
Entitled to Use	4 (4%)

student and teacher beliefs about multitasking; an independent t-test was conducted. Table 6 shows means and standard deviations for teacher and student multitasking beliefs. Students and teachers rated their multitasking beliefs by selecting a number on a Likert Scale (1 = People can only focus on one thing at a time; 4 = Some people can focus on multiple things, while others cannot; to 7 = Everybody can

TABLE 6 Multitasking Beliefs

Groups	N	Mean	SD	S Error Mean	No response
Teachers	289	2.96	1.22	.07	0
Students	159	3.65	1.11	.09	4

multitask).

Hypothesis number three investigated whether teachers have been distracted by student cell phone use versus if students have noticed a teacher being distracted by cell phones, a chi-square was conducted.

Table 7 shows the frequencies and percentages for teachers versus students across response options. With alpha equal to .05, a chi-square test on

TABLE 7: Comparison of teachers being distracted by versus student's perceptions of teachers being distracted by cell Phones.

Groups	YES	NO
Teachers	250 (87%)	39 (13%)
students	80 (49%)	82 (51%)

these frequencies was statistically significant ($\chi^2 (1, N = 451) = 72.87, r = .40$). This indicates that teachers reported being distracted reported being distracted by a student using a cell phone more than students perceived teachers to be distracted from students using cell phones.

Table 8 shows how students viewed teachers handling distraction, if they believe teachers get distracted by cell phone usage, and Table 9 shows how teachers reported typically handling being distracted by student cell phones usage. Two raters read all responses and labeled them into categories. Once the raters agreed upon the categories,

both individuals response under a certain category.

After initial coding, there was an 87% inter-rater agreement for how students view the teacher handling distraction and a 91% inter-rater agreement for how teachers handle being distracted. After discussion and

Action	Frequency
Tell student to put the phone away/on silent	49 (53%)
Warning/stare at student/confront student	13 (14%)
Ask student to leave class	10(11%)
Ignore student	7(8%)
Take phone from students	6 (6%)
Ask questions to alert students	5(5%)
Remind student of cell phone policy	3(3%)

Action	Frequency
Tell student to put the phone away/on silent	70 (21%)
Make a general comment about phone policy	57 (17%)
Ignore the student and continue teaching	52 (15%)
Confront the student/speak directly to the student	45 (13%)
Stare at the student	27 (8%)
Discuss his/her cell phone use after class	27 (8%)
Ask the student to leave the classroom	22 (7%)
Involve the student's with a task/ question	18 (5%)
Take the student's cell phone	10 (3%)

debate, the raters came to a 100% agreement on the both set of responses and their appropriate codes.

Discussion

The hypothesis of students being more likely to believe cell phones

should be used in class was supported by student and teacher responses. Students believed that "yes, phones should be allowed during class, but usage should be kept to a minimal." However, based on the responses, teachers significantly stated that, "no, they did not believe

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students should be allowed to use cell phones during class" ($r = .25$). Interestingly, even though the majority of teachers did not believe students should use cell phones during class, 7% of teachers still thought students should be allowed to use cell phones as much as they please.

The second hypothesis stated that students would be more likely to believe individuals have the ability to multitask. As previously noted, Cepada (2013) found that college undergraduate students were observed to be multitasking, or using their cell phones, 42% of the time during class. Based on the current study's results, students ($\bar{x} = 3.65$) are significantly more likely than faculty ($\bar{x} = 2.96$) to believe that individuals have the ability to multitask ($r = .40$). If students believe that they can multitask, it could lead to them believing that they should be allowed to use their cell phones during class (Kuzenkoff et al., 2015). Based on the number of students who rated a five or higher on their multitasking belief, meaning they are more in favor of believing individuals can multitask, 73% believed they should be able to use their phone during class. As well, based on the number of teachers who rated

five or higher on their multitasking belief, 40% allow students to use their cell phones during class.

According to the teachers who rated three or below on their multitasking belief, meaning they are more in favor of believing that individuals can only focus on one thing at a time, 63% did not allow students to use their cell phones during class. And if teachers don't believe individuals can multitask, it could be distracting when they see a student texting during a lecture.

The third hypothesis stated that teachers will be more likely to think that student cell phone usage during class is a distraction compared to students. After testing this hypothesis, the findings indicated that teachers self-report being distracted significantly more than students believe teachers are being distracted ($r = .40$). About half of the students had noticed that teachers had been distracted by cell phones usage in class, whereas about half marked that they had never noticed a teacher being distracted by a student using a cell phone. However, a large majority of the teachers who responded indicated that they had been distracted by students using cell phones in class. Students may have realized that using phones

are distracting to themselves and may or may not have a true understanding that cell phones can be distracting to other students around them (Sana, Weston, & Cepeda, 2013). However, it is unlikely students believe their cell phone use is distracting to the teacher, as 51% of students who completed the questionnaire indicated they have never noticed a teacher being distracted.

Regarding general cell phone usage in the classroom, results showed that students brought their phones to class more often than teachers. Teachers from the survey said that, on average, students were using their phones almost seven times per class.

However, only a small percentage (5%) said they were distracted multiple times per day by the use of cell phones. Students also noted that being able to send and receive text messages in their class was neither difficult nor easy.

It is known that students using cell phones during class are experiencing negative side effects with their academic achievement (Junco, 2012). Whether students realize it or not, their classroom cell phone usage is also leading to negative side effects on other students in proximity (Wood, et al., 2012). Students may believe that using a

cell phone during class is a personal choice and will only affect themselves. However, cell phone usage could indirectly have a negative impact on the entire class by negatively affecting the teacher. Teachers don't believe students should use phones during class because they don't believe students can use their phone and pay attention to instruction simultaneously. Even though approximately half of the students believe cell phone use is distracting to teacher, a vast majority of teachers (87%) consider it distracting to their teaching. Ultimately, if schools truly want their students to perform the best they can academically, prohibiting the use of phones in class should be the only cell phone policy.

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